

Time Series Problems in the Energy Sector

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Abstract—Public Power Corporation (PPC) is the leading South East European electric utility, with its activities covering all aspects of the energy sector: from coal mining and the management of thermal power plants to renewables and e-mobility. PPC is implementing a major digital transformation plan, which aims to transform it into a data-driven company, thus improving the efficiency and effectiveness of its operations. To this end, PPC's R&D department is working on addressing numerous data analytics tasks, which typically involve (multivariate) time series. In this work, we describe these tasks, stressing their business importance and criticality. We also briefly describe our current solutions and propose directions for future improvements.

Index Terms—time series, energy sector, data analytics, machine learning

I. INTRODUCTION

PPC constitutes the largest electricity company in South-eastern Europe, with presence in Greece, Romania and North Macedonia. In the past, its energy generation capabilities relied heavily on thermal power stations, but the last few years, emphasis has been placed on replacing them with renewable energy resources in combination with gas-fired power stations. In Greece alone, PPC currently operates four large gas-fired power stations with a total capacity of 2.7 GW. and 92 RES parks with an installed capacity of more than 700MW, while the goal is to reach 4GW in the next few years. The maintenance of these plants and parks entails a significant burden, given that they are scattered all over the country.

To reduce the ensuing maintenance cost, PPC is exploring ways of automating the detection of disruptions in the normal operation of this infrastructure, due to material failure, dysfunctions or even cyber or physical attacks. In the context of PPC's digital transformation, this task has been assigned to our R&D department. More specifically, our goal is to gather all useful information that can be extracted from plant equipment, to model the corresponding problem as a learning task and to propose initial AI-based solutions that will be later refined to ensure higher effectiveness, time efficiency and usability.

Below, we describe the main maintenance problems defined so far. They all involve high-dimensional time series that give

rise to learning tasks over data streams. For each problem, we discuss the related equipment, the data that is extracted from it, the formal definition of the corresponding learning task, the current solution and finally, ideas for future improvements.

II. PHOTOVOLTAIC POWER STATION

Equipment. PPC is experimenting with a photovoltaic (PV) power station, which consists of four independent units with a nominal production capacity of 0.5 MW each. A PV inverter on each unit converts the Direct Current (DC) output of the solar panel into Alternating Current (AC). At the utility frequency of 50 Hz, the AC current from each PV inverter is fed to a step-up transformer, which raises the voltage so that the power can be injected to the distribution grid.

Data. The operation of the PV is described by 34 features, which are distinguished into two categories: those stemming from the operation of each PV inverter and those related to the generated electricity. For example, the former include the water temperature and the heat sink temperature, while the latter entail the AC active power and DC power production, the maximum power point voltage and current, the AC current per phase, the line-to-line voltage (uv, vw, wu), the line frequency, the line reactive power, and the line apparent power. All features are independently retrieved from the four PV inverters with a sampling period of 1 minute.

Problem. The PV inverters are connected to the operational technology network of PPC in order to monitor and control their functionalities. As a result, the PV station is vulnerable to cyber-attacks, where malicious actors might target the availability of the PV inverters or inject malicious commands into them, leading to wrong control operations that damage the PV components or even propagate the effects to the wider electricity infrastructure through the grid. To avoid such cases, we need to address the following anomaly detection problem, based on the time series data described above:

Given the 34 features continuously generated by the PV's four inverters, train AI models that: (i) decide whether the latest data (within a window of W minutes) indicates a

potential anomaly or the effects of a cyber-attack, and (ii) suggest the optimal reconfiguration of the grid in order to minimise the cascading effects.

Note that the common size of window W is 1 minute. Note also that this problem is quite generic, applying to all PVs connected to the grid. Hence, the solution to this problem will be applied to all solar farms operated by PPC.

Solution. A custom web server application provides the grid model of the PV infrastructure in real-time in pandapower format¹, continuously retrieving the latest measurements. A grid model represents the electricity grid (in JSON format), including the current topology and the latest measurements from each measurement point of that topology. In case of a cyber or a physical attack against the PV inverters, a security event triggers the *intentional islanding* tool to retrieve the latest grid model and inspect the impact of the attack to the local power grid of the PV infrastructure. Based on the security event information, the trained model decides to isolate the affected inverter (e.g., in case it has an increased cyber-risk). This intentional islanding is carried out by an unsupervised, self-learning deep neural network [1]. Subsequently, the tool solves the power flow problem of the new grid model, suggesting a new configuration to the PV station operator. Alternatively, the new configuration can be automatically applied through the Modbus TCP communication interfaces of the inverters.

Future work. We intend to enhance the effectiveness of the current solution by incorporating data stream summarization techniques into its feature generation process. Our goal is to efficiently capture information from longer periods of time, thus increasing the accuracy of our model without any significant impact on its training and prediction times.

III. NETWORK TRAFFIC FROM INDUSTRIAL DEVICES

Equipment. The Industrial Internet of Things laboratory of the PPC Innovation Hub is equipped with various industrial devices shown in Figure 1 that are used in power plants, remote monitoring and power automation processes. Such devices are programmable logic controllers (PLCs), remote terminal units (RTUs), variable frequency drives, phasor measurement units and energy meters. Those devices are using specialised communication protocols (e.g. Modbus TCP, Profinet, etc), which do not leverage protection mechanisms, encryption or authentication. Therefore, they are vulnerable to cyber-attacks, with potential impact on the physical systems that they control.

Data. The network traffic of these industrial devices is represented as 5-tuple network flows, which are formed, based on the following criteria:

- 1) The flow timeout, i.e., the maximum duration of the flow.
- 2) The 5-tuple features of the network packets, i.e., the source IP address, the source transport-layer port, the destination IP address, the destination transport-layer port, and the transport-layer protocol.

For example, a 5-tuple record can be: 192.168.21.225-192.168.21.70-43446-80-6,

¹<https://www.pandapower.org/>

Fig. 1: The industrial devices of PPC, including the exterior of a PLC cabinet (upper left), the interior of the PLC cabinet (upper right), energy meters installed on a PV panel (lower left), and a phasor measurement unit with an EV charger (lower right).

where 192.168.21.225 is the source IP address, 192.168.21.70 is the destination IP address, 43446 is the source TCP port, 80 is the destination TCP port, and 6 denotes the transport-layer protocol, i.e., TCP in this case. Note that each network flow is bidirectional, with the first packet determining the forward direction (i.e., source to destination). As a result, each flow is associated with different statistics for the forward and the backward direction.

More specifically, these statistics describe 82 properties of the packets included in each flow. Indicatively, they include: the flow duration in microseconds, the total number and total size of packets for each direction, statistics relevant to the size of packets (maximum, minimum, mean size, standard deviation) and the inter-arrival time between two consecutive packets per direction, the number of flags activated on the packets at the transport layer for each direction, the rate of packets in the forward and backward direction as well as statistics for the active and idle time of the flow [2].

Problem. Our goal is to detect cyber-attacks that could target the availability and integrity of industrial devices using Modbus TCP. Despite the critical role that these devices have on the proper operation of automation and the safety

procedures inside an industrial facility, they are characterised by constrained computing resources, while the underlying communication protocol is vulnerable to unauthorized activities. For example, a flooding denial-of-service attack may degrade the performance of these devices, or render them unavailable, thus risking the operation of the industrial facility. Timely detection of such activities is crucial in order to plan for remedial actions. To this end, we need to address the following problem by analysing the network traffic of those devices in terms of network flows, given that their statistics are affected in the case of a flooding cyber-attack:

Given the 82 features of the 5-tuple network flow, train a model that decides whether the latest data (within a window of W minutes) involves malicious activities.

Note that this definition is generic, covering any network.

Solution. The network traffic of the industrial devices, which is in the form of packet capture, is aggregated into 5-tuple network flows by using the CICFlowMeter tool². To train the model, we generated a dataset that includes the network traffic during normal operation and during cyber-attacks. The dataset is labelled by using a dedicated IP address for the cyber-attacker, which conducted the flooding denial-of-service attack. Then, ML models (e.g. decision trees and random forests) are trained on the labelled data to classify flows that indicate Modbus TCP cyber-attacks. Evaluation results show that accuracy and F1 amount to 96,4% and 74.9%, resp. [3].

Future work. We intend to further increase the F1 score of our solution by incorporating more advanced models on the labelled data, based on deep neural networks.

IV. EV CHARGING DATA

Equipment. PPC maintains the largest network of EV chargers in Greece, with more than 2,000 charging points nationwide³. These chargers are publicly available to any EV owner, with an increasing number of transactions occurring every month. It is critical, therefore, to ensure the resilience and robustness of this infrastructure against cyber-attacks and to optimize the use of the renewables through a dynamic tariff scheme that promotes green charging, so as to make the most of renewables when charging EVs.

A. EV Charging Sessions

Data. In the course of a charging session, the EV charging station periodically sends measurements related to the state of charge of the EV battery, the voltage values for each phase, and the consumed Watt-hours (Whs) throughout the session. The availability of measurands depends on the capabilities of the EV charging station, while their frequency is determined by the administrator. A common frequency is 10 seconds. The values of these features during the entire charging session form a *charging curve*.

This information is gathered by the *charging station management system* (CSMS), the central platform where every EV

²<https://github.com/KirKenx/CICFlowmeterV4>

³<https://www.deiblue.com/location>

(a) Normal charging curve

(b) Tampered charging curve

Fig. 2: The two types of EV charging curves.

charging station is connected to centrally manage and monitor its session. The content and the format of the data exchange is determined by OCPP protocol, version 1.6 [4].

Problem. The confidentiality, availability and integrity of charging sessions is of paramount importance, due to privacy issues (as foreseen by EU's general data protection regulation) as well as due to business and user needs (as they determine the amount paid by the EV owner and received by the charge point operator). These three requirements can be violated through a cyber-attack, e.g., through a man-in-the-middle attack that modifies the Whs transmitted by the EV charging station to the CSMS. To ensure the integrity of charging sessions, the following task should be addressed:

Train a binary classification model that receives as input an EV charging curve and decides whether it is abnormal or not, i.e., whether its data have been tampered or not.

For clarity, the two types of EV charging curves are depicted in Figure 2.

Solution. Our solution consists of a regression model

trained over a dataset comprising 10 charging sessions. Among them, 7 are normal and 3 have been modified through a false data injection attack. The solution actually leverages an ARIMA model.

Future work. To enhance the effectiveness of our ARIMA model, we plan to generate a large-scale dataset with abnormal charging sessions. We will apply the trained model to all charging curves in PPC’s network of EV chargers throughout the years 2022 and 2023. Those classified as abnormal will be manually checked for verification. The resulting set of abnormal charging curves will be used for re-training our model so as to make it operational, integrating it into PPC’s CSMS.

B. EV Charging Transactions

Data. Thousands of transactions take place every week in PPC’s network of EV chargers. They are described by the following attributes: the start and end timestamp, the total volume delivered power (in KWh), the charging point information (i.e., its id, street address, city ect), the authentication id, the maximum power that can be delivered by the charging point (e.g., 22KW) and the sojourn time, i.e., the time the EV was parked and plugged into the charging station.

Problem. PPC is interested in defining charging profiles so as to identify patterns in EV users’ behavior that allow for optimizing the consumption of energy from renewables, while lowering the cost for its users. To this end, we need to address the following task, based on the above data:

Given the data describing EV charging transactions, define EV user profiles with respect to charging needs, places of charging, and parking time that are suitable for creating a set of services adapted to different needs and user behaviours.

This task lends itself naturally to an unsupervised, clustering process that is evaluated through the silhouette coefficient as well as the Davies-Bouldin index and the Calinski-Harabasz index. However, considering exclusively these metrics might lead to a large number of user clusters or, in most cases, to just two, with the largest of them containing almost all transaction records. Such results, though, are of limited utility, as they are neither useful nor interpretable, i.e., they cannot be associated with meaningful, distinctive user behaviours. For this reason, the *quantitative evaluation* is accompanied by a *qualitative* one that characterizes the behavior of each cluster with EV users according to its business value.

Solution. To address the above problem, a data analytics pipeline was implemented. Initially, data cleaning removed records with missing or noisy/outlier values (e.g., where the charging time is higher than the sojourn time). Next, feature selection identified the most useful features, namely the start timestamp, the volume and the sojourn time. Finally, we applied a wide range of established clustering algorithms that cover all main types in the literature: from the representative-based ones (K-Means and Expectation Maximization) to hierarchical and graph clustering ones (i.e., connected components, center, merge-center, ricochet, correlation, markov and cut clustering) [5]. Setting K=10, K-means exhibited the

Fig. 3: The Combined-Cycle Power Station Unit.

best quantitative and qualitative performance than all other algorithms. For example, some of the defined profiles are the following: (i) morning to afternoon, high energy, long-term stay, (ii) early evening, low energy, short-term stay, (iii) early afternoon, medium energy, medium-term stay, (iv) evening to next morning, medium energy, long-term.

Future work. Our current solution operates on a snapshot of the EV charging transactions, through a batch process that ignores the challenges of data streams. Our goal is to turn it into a dynamic, stream-based solution that supports concept drift in an incremental way, i.e, without the need of periodically retraining the learned model to all available data.

V. COMBINED-CYCLE POWER STATION

Equipment. As mentioned above, PPC operates large gas-fired power stations that are critical for supporting renewables at times with limited energy production (i.e., during nighttime and gentle winds for the solar and the wind farms, respectively). Therefore, special care is taken to ensure their proper operation, protecting them against cyber-physical attacks. To this end, PPC experiments with the combined-cycle gas-fired power station that is depicted in Figure 3.

Data. The operation of this power station is described by 48 measurements from the distributed control system of a specific unit of the power station. They are related to the proper operation of various automation and safety mechanisms of the unit and the step-up transformer, i.e., they include temperatures from various setpoints, pressure of inlets, filters and water, measurements of vibration as well as electricity measurements pertaining to the power production while the unit is in operation: the national dispatch centre market setpoint, the current and active power from the transmission side, and the voltage measurements from various setpoints of the unit.

Problem. The above data are used for two purposes:

- 1) For predictive maintenance, in particular for predicting future faults by analysing the historical data, and
- 2) For detecting indications of a cyber-physical attack that affects important operations of the power plant unit (e.g., a

Fig. 4: The Surge Power Generator.

cyber-attack against a PLC that causes dysfunction of the cooling process, leading to high temperatures).

Both problems are accommodated by the following generic definition, which applies to any similar unit:

Given the time series of the above 48 features for a window of size W , identify uncommon measurements that deviate significantly from the normal operation of the gas-fired power plant unit.

Common values for W are 20, 30 and 50 minutes [6].

Solution. To address the above problem, we applied a data analytics methodology for anomaly detection [6]. First, standardisation ensures zero-mean and unit variance for each feature. Then, every vectorial feature $\mathbf{m} = [x, y]$ is converted into its complex representation, i.e., $z = x + iy$. Finally, several established algorithms for supervised learning were applied, receiving as input the complex feature vector of the sliding window W . Among others, stochastic outlier selection (SOS) and deep fully connected autoencoders were considered. The experimental results demonstrate the superiority of SOS in combination with complex features and $W=50$ minutes.

Future work. To increase the effectiveness of the trained model in outlier detection, we will explore more advanced deep neural networks that are crafted for multi-dimensional time series, like RNNs and LSTMs.

VI. SURGE TESTING POWER GENERATOR

Equipment. The PPC Innovation Hub is equipped with a 10 MW surge-testing power generator that is unique in Greece⁴ (see Figure 4). It is used for short circuit tests breaking capacity and for interrupting performance tests on low, medium and high voltage apparatus.

Data. The operational data of the surge-power generator describes its proper operation during the tests as well as its condition during idle time (i.e., when no tests are conducted). The included measurements are: the existence of voltage for

each phase, a flag indicating the acquisition of rated rounds per minute for the generator and the exciter, flags indicating over-voltage and over-current, the voltage of the 24 V battery, the generator motor speed, the generator and the exciter voltage and current, and the temperatures from the cooling water, the windings and the outlet air. In total, 17 features are defined.

Problem. Similar to Section V, the data provided by the surge-power generator can be used for detecting cyber-attacks and for predictive maintenance of the generator. Hence, the following tasks should be addressed:

Given the time series of the above 17 features for a sliding window of size W , identify uncommon measurements that deviate significantly from the normal operation of the surge-power generator.

Solution. We applied the same methodology for anomaly detection as in Section V, reaching similar conclusions for the relative performance of the considered ML and DL algorithms.

Future work. Similar to Section V, we intent to explore more advanced deep neural networks for time series analysis, like RNNs and LSTMs.

VII. PREDICTIVE MAINTENANCE ON INDUSTRIAL DEVICES

Equipment. As mentioned above, the Industrial Internet of Things laboratory in the PPC Innovation Hub is equipped with an RTU that is responsible for monitoring the surge-testing power generator as well as other critical industrial equipment. It is therefore critical to monitor RTU's state and its ability to correctly control the connected devices.

Data. The operational data of the RTU comprise the following 21 features: 'CPU_USAGE' which is the level of CPU used, 'DOING_WELL' denoting that the RTU is running ok, 'FAIL_CONF' denoting a failure in the configuration, 'FAIL_PLC' denoting that the programmed logic is stopped, 'FAIL_PS1' denoting a failure of the main power supply, 'FAIL_RTU' described as a general failure of the RTU (watchdog, configuration), 'FAIL_SYNC1' denoting a failure in the primary synchronization source, 'FAIL_SYNC2' denoting a failure in the secondary synchronization source, 'FAIL_SYNCDESV' denoting a deviation in synchronization bigger than 3 ms, 'FAIL_SYNCHW' denoting a hardware failure, 'LINK_LNC0' which is a link in ETH2, 'LINK_LNC1' which is a link in ETH3, 'LINK_LNC2' which is a link in ETH4, 'LINK_MOTFEC0' which is a link in ETH1, 'MEM_USAGE' denoting the RAM memory usage (%), 'PLC_WARNING' denoting that the programmed logic is missing some signals, 'PS1_V' denoting the voltage of the main power supply, 'RTU_HEALTH' which is a double digital signal indicating the general health of the RTU (range 0-3), 'TEMP' denoting the CPU temperature, 'WARN_BAT' which is a low battery warning and 'WARN_PS1', denoting that the voltage of the main power supply is under the warning limit. Each feature is updated and collected every 5 minutes.

Problem. Using the above features, the following predictive maintenance task should be addressed:

⁴<https://innovationhub.dei.gr/en/services/testing/ergasthria-hlektrikon-dokimon-metrhseon/high-power-laboratory/>

Given the value of the 21 features for a window of size W , train AI models that: (i) forecast their future distribution and (ii) identify measurements that deviate significantly from RTU's normal operation.

In our experiments, we set the window size to 15,750 minutes, i.e., almost 11 days of data capturing and storing [7].

Solution. To address this problem, a data science pipeline was implemented [7]. Initially, data cleaning removed records with missing or noisy values. Next, feature selection removed the superfluous attributes, i.e., those exhibiting a zero standard deviation and a mean value equal or very close to one or zero. Among the remaining features ('CPU_USAGE', 'TEMP', 'RTU_HEALTH', 'PS1_V' and 'MEM_USAGE'), three were selected based on their variation and on domain knowledge:

- 1) 'CPU_USAGE', which denotes the proportion of the CPU time that is busy executing tasks compared to the total time.
- 2) 'MEM_USAGE', which indicates the amount of memory resources actively used by programs, applications, and the operating system itself.
- 3) 'TEMP', which reports the temperature measured inside the RTU by installed sensors. Monitoring the temperature is crucial to ensure proper functioning, prevent overheating, and maintain system stability in the RTU.

Fig. 5: Pearson correlation of the selected RTU features.

Note that these features have no strong correlation with one another, as shown in Figure 5. This verifies that they capture different behavioral patterns within the RTU. Finally, the selected features were normalized in the range of 0 to 1.

On the resulting feature set, we applied a wide range of established supervised learning algorithms. For the time series forecasting task, three different approaches were tested, namely a deep learning one (LSTM), a statistical one (ARIMA) and a gradient-boosted tree (XGBOOST). For the anomaly detection task, we implemented two deep learning approaches, i.e., an LSTM Autoencoder and a deep convolutional autoencoder together with an isolation forest (an ensemble binary tree method), and DBSCAN (a clustering method).

Future work. We intend to integrate our solution with the real-time data stream from the RTU. Thus, we can timely capture the predicted anomalies by implementing real-time predictions as far into the future as possible, increasing the time available to the field engineers for repairing the equipment.

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